

Background brief for Country

Country: Country

Date of update: add here

Contributors: for new contributors ADD YOUR NAME HERE

 This is a document for filling information about specific country (all are [link to shared folder for contributors and users])

 Master document containing general information about the project, empty template with prompts and links to other countries is here [link to shared folder for contributors and users]

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Guidelines for template:

- These are *prompts*, inviting to search and describe.
- Feel free to skip some of them, propose new prompts and add relevant points
- **Do not feel like you have to fill all of them!**
- Feel empowered to ask for help and/or pass the message to those who have more expertise, delegate!
- Where possible, please include **numbers** and **sources**
- Feel free to use both **English AND** your **NATIONAL** language - it would be great to have it in English so that information can be **shared** with other countries, and of

course it is important to have a national language for **communication with policymakers and stakeholders**

- **To navigate** within the document, you can use **Outline (on the left side of the document interface or by Table of Contents)**
- Feel free to type inside of the document

Background brief for Country

What is in the news?

What has happened recently in relation to the academic system, to mental health, to the career of researchers, to funding, to research culture, to equity, diversity, inclusion (EDI) topics?

→ *Tips:* Check in your local language. Ask colleagues. Include links to the sources of information.

For example:

- Describe the recent events in the news related to academia, mental health, employment conditions
- Hot topics in the social media (Twitter, about mental health, academic chatter etc)
- Changes in the legislation, reforms in relation to academia & mental health
- What is being spoken in the parliament etc? Any relevant events recently?
- If nothing is there, or not spoken - it is also important to note and write down. What seems to be “not even on our agenda”?
- What seems to be urgent?

Feel free to type here

Funding for research and academia

Briefly describe the structure and snapshot of funding for research and academia, example:

- The investment into research and academia from the government and private sectors. Amount GDP% to the research funding
- Any recent major reforms to the funding schemes
- Describe the prospects for the future

Feel free to type here

Persona of the researcher on the career ladder in the country

Describe the persona of the researcher in the country, the one you are most familiar with, for example:

- Describe some of the statistics (background and demography) of the researchers in the country - age range, prevalence of international researchers among different career stages / types of institutes, gender distribution
- Describe the recent trends in relation to that
- Describe the active plans (policies) aiming at improving the balance or anything related to previous

Feel free to type here

Academic system in the country

Provide an overview of what the research ecosystem looks like in your country.

For example:

- The number and size of institutes/research centres/universities
 - Any clusters and networks of research entities (e.g. universities, academies, research institutes).
 - The distribution of research-intensive, teaching-intensive, mixed centres, business schools?
 - The status of universities and research centres (if autonomous, public servants, private, etc)
- *Tips:* This type of information can be found in the [national portals of the Euraxess](#), and national portals for Open Science by [OpenAire](#)

Feel free to type here

Career track for researcher in the country

Describe the aspects of the researcher career structures in the country, for example:

- The general career track for the researcher
- The level of precarity and sustainability of an academic research career - PhD holders, fellowships, open positions, tenure track systems; status as civil / public servant
- The distribution of permanent and temporary staff at different career stages
- The principal performance evaluation/assessment system for career advancement, e.g. publications, grant income, other factors
- Any specific programs of support and training/development for predoctoral/doctoral students
- The definition of early career researchers (ECR) and any specific programs of support and training/development for them
- Any country-specific aspects of the researcher career structure, e.g. brain drain, leaky pipeline, internationalisation drive

Climate around mental health and well-being - in general and in academia

Describe Mental health and well-being in the country and in academia specifically. For example:

- Describe the level of general public awareness (e.g. generated via mental health campaigns in the public domain)
- Describe the level of National/regional burden of mental disorders in the country, e.g. [here](#) or [here](#)
- Describe research studies about mental health and well-being in the academic workplace in your country (if any) Check ReMO [Zotero library](#) with community-sourced articles
- Describe available data from surveys (even a particular subset of researchers would be valuable)

Feel free to type here

Mental health support and service systems

Please choose prompts:

- Describe mental health interventions typically available within the country
- Describe barriers to providing resources
- Describe barriers to accessing resources
- Describe the level of subscription of services (are available services over-subscribed?)
- Describe effectiveness of available resources
- Describe the financing of the access to service - cover by state, insurance, divided, out-of-pocket?
- Describe available mental health aid/counselling available at the institutions (if any, if different from general healthcare)
- For example, is there a system of Mental Health First Aid service or training, is it available in the institutions/organizations

Feel free to type here

Workplace of academia, employment

Think of academia from “just another workplace” perspective.

- Describe national employment practices and laws for researchers - for ECR, PhDs, tenure-track, faculty, temporary/permanent contracts

- That may include type of contract, working hours, entitlement for holidays and sabbaticals, duty of care on employer, social security burden on employer vs researcher
- Describe the most common healthcare system/insurance used by researchers (public, private, in relation to their employment status)

Feel free to type here

Policy view on mental health/ well-being

- Describe any national or regional legislation on mental health, workplace, anti-discrimination, protected groups
- Describe the level of discussion among policy-makers of topics related to mental health in general population, workplace-specific, academia-specific
- Describe what is the legal relationship of researcher and entity (institution) in case of harassment and bullying
- Describe any formalised procedures within institutions regarding their duty of care for mental health issues of employees (researchers)
- Describe if any procedures exist to track the effectiveness of anti-discrimination or anti-bullying measures at the universities

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Stakeholders and policies

- Describe the major organisations involved in the recognition and improvement of the status of researchers or subset of researchers
- Describe any organisation or initiative in the country that is advocating for the mental health and well-being of researchers (or something with close goals via career development, training etc)?
- Describe how the country organisations/institutions (research stakeholders) participate in the Mental Health awareness week. What are the barriers?

Feel free to type here

Euraxess centers as hubs for supporting researchers' mobility and career

- Describe Euraxess centres are there in the country and how active are they in directly or indirectly supporting researchers, including in terms of mental health and well-being
- Describe number of organisations/institutions that have been given the HR Excellence in Research Award
- Describe number of organisations/institutions that have endorsed and adhere to The European Charter for Researchers and The Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (aka Charter & Code).
- Describe the situation with Adherence and Effectiveness of OTM-R (recruitment)

- Describe any relevant national/regional R&I (research & innovation) related policies
- What are the local (country) excellence awards to the organisations/institutions? What do they assess for, briefly?
- Describe national policies/ analogues of “Charter&Code” exist in the country. Do they have well-being or mental health recommendations in them?
- Describe the role and place of trade unions, professional associations and organisations, which support researchers in the country
- (e.g. in Sweden: The Swedish Association of University Teachers and Researchers, SULF, see saco.se website)

Feel free to type here

Equity, diversity, inclusion, accessibility in academia

Equity, diversity, inclusion, accessibility efforts are linked to mental health and well-being at the workplace.

Reflect and share your thoughts on the questions

- How can we leverage the link?
- Which type of information do we need to search for and gather?

For example, describe:

- Diversity & Inclusion Approach or Strategy signed, implemented in the research institutions

Feel free to type here

National culture

Each country has its own national culture which affects the expectations of people and their communications. It is different from organizational culture. It would be curious to keep that in mind when looking later together at the data (and practices) on mental health of researchers in different countries.

Please check the Hofstede- developed resource to “profile” your national culture and share below: <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/>

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Feel free to type here

P Parking lot for information that did not fit into the prompts

Please add here information that did not fit into the previous prompts, but is relevant and important for the country context:

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Feel free to type here

Feedback and discussion

Notes, insights and questions in relation to the template and the process:

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Feel free to type here